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PRAVO DETETA NA ZDRAVLJE

Ovaj rad analizira dvostruku složenost ostvarivanja prava deteta na zdravlje u pravnom sistemu Republike Srbije. Najpre, analizira se težišna tačka ovog prava iskazana standardom najviši nivo zdravstvene i medicinske zaštite, te socio-ekonomske obaveze države s tim u vezi. U središnjem delu, isputuju se granice autonomije deteta na odlučivanje o svom zdravlju, pojmovi razvojne sposobnosti (*evolving capacity*) i sposobnosti za rasuđivanje (*Gillick competence*) kao osnova informisanog pristanka deteta. Posebna pažnja posvećena je pravima deteta na privatnost i poverljivost zdravstvenih podataka, te osetljivim ulogama roditelja i lekara u njegovom ostvarivanju. Istražuju se kriterijumi rešavanja etičke dileme lekara izazvane mogućim sukobom njegovih profesionalnih dužnosti poštovanja privatnosti deteta, s jedne strane, i postupanja u njegovom najboljem interesu, s druge. Razmatraju se granični slučajevi (poput prekida trudnoće ili estetskih zahvata) gde je narušavanje poverljivosti opravdano isključivo zaštitom najboljeg interesa deteta od neposredne i ozbiljne opasnosti po njegov život i zdravlje.

Ključne reči: Konvencija o pravima deteta, zdravlje, najviši dostizni nivo zdravstvene zaštite, privatnost i poverljivost, najbolji interes deteta, profesionalne dužnosti lekara, prava i obaveze roditelja.

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THE CHILD'S RIGHT TO HEALTH

This paper examines the dual complexity of exercising the child's right to health in the legal system of the Republic of Serbia. It first analyses the core dimension of this right expressed in the enjoyment of the highest attainable health and medical protection standards, as well as the related socio-economic obligations of the state. The central part explores the limits of a child's autonomy in health-related decision-making processes, addressing the concepts of evolving capacity and Gillick competence as bases for a minor's informed consent. Particular attention is given to the child's rights to privacy and confidentiality of health information, and to the sensitive roles and duties of parents and physicians in exercising these rights. The paper further explores and critically evaluates the criteria for resolving the ethical dilemma faced by physicians in cases where their duties to respect a child's privacy conflict with duties to act in the child's best interests. The author also considers borderline cases (such as termination of pregnancy or elective aesthetic procedures), where breaching confidentiality may be justified only to protect the child from an imminent and serious risk to life or health.

Keywords: Convention on the Rights of the Child, health, enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health, privacy and confidentiality, the best interest of the child, professional duties of physicians, parental rights and duties.